

DiSSCo related output

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Title

DiSSCo Prepare Milestone report MS 5.3 "Documentation of PIDs relevant for DiSSCo technical infrastructure"

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Abstract

The DiSSCo Prepare Milestone report MS5.3 "Documentation of PIDs relevant for DiSSCo technical infrastructure" compiles information on different persistent identifiers and discusses its relevance to DiSSCo. Different alternative Handle-based PID schemes are discussed. While not all PIDs will be directly used by the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data architecture of the DiSSCo research infrastructure, it is important to be aware of other developments for interoperability reasons.

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DiSSCo Prepare WP5 – Milestone report

MS5.3 Documentation of PIDs relevant for DiSSCo technical infrastructure

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Abstract

The DiSSCo Prepare Milestone report MS5.3 "Documentation of PIDs relevant for DiSSCo technical infrastructure" compiles information on different persistent identifiers and discusses its relevance to DiSSCo. Different alternative Handle-based PID schemes are discussed. While not all PIDs will be directly used by the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) data architecture of the DiSSCo research infrastructure, it is important to be aware of other developments for interoperability reasons.

Keywords

PID, PID schemes

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1. Introduction & background

The Distributed System of Scientific Collections ([DiSSCo](#)) is a new Research Infrastructure (RI) of European natural science collections (NSC) currently in its Preparatory phase ([DiSSCo Prepare](#)). The DiSSCo RI aims to create a new business model for one European collection that digitally unifies all European natural science assets under common access, curation, policies and practices that ensure that all the data is easily Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR principles; Wilkinson et al. 2016).

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are an essential element of global data infrastructures and fundamental for the digital transformation of collections-based science. They facilitate unambiguous citation and tracking of physical samples thus allowing linking of specimens, data and publications; and serve as identifiers but also connectors. Such connections can be recognized by both machines and humans (machine- and human-readable), which reveals and gives access to a wide range of associated information, ensuring that relationships can be understood, knowledge gained and conclusions to be reached.

Acting as a long-lasting reference to a digital entity or resource, PIDs are used to uniquely and unambiguously identify digital representations of natural science objects. PIDs are identifiers that are **globally unique, resolvable** (i.e. can be expressed as an URI which can take users or machines to a resource or information about a resource) and they are actively managed so that they remain persistent in the long term. Therefore, PIDs play an important role in digital preservation of data.

Persistent identifiers were originally developed to address challenges arising from the distributed and disorganised nature of the internet and the so-called “link rot” that made it difficult to maintain a persistent record or digital resources including research data (see Klump & Huber 2017 and references within). PIDs have been in use for over 20 years and there is ongoing discussion on which PID schemes to use in a given community.

There are several types, categories and levels to broadly group PIDs (see Meadows et al. 2019):

- identifiers for researchers, organizations, and research objects and outputs;
- open, i.e. fully interoperable vs. proprietary, i.e. for use within a single organization;
- local to an individual organization, national or global.

A highly desirable quality for PIDs is to have FAIR metadata. As well as significantly reducing the risk of reference rot, this enables the discovery of open, interoperable, well-defined (FAIR) metadata containing provenance information in a predictable manner – and the PIDs themselves are also open. DOIs are a good example.

For DiSSCo's envisaged FAIR Digital Object (FDO) infrastructure, PIDs for the digital objects should be based on the [Handle system](#) to be compliant with the Digital Object Architecture as described by the DONA foundation and CORDRA as its reference implementation. There are currently eight PID schemes using the Handle system which could potentially be used as a PID scheme for a Digital Specimen, these have been described in Hardisty et al. (2021):

- Digital Object Identifier ([DOI](#))
- International GeoSample Number ([IGSN](#))
- European PID Consortium ([ePIC](#))

- Five-digit prefix ([CNRI](#))
- Second-level prefix
- Three-segment prefix
- Two-digit top level prefix
- National-level services

A PID scheme relates not only to the technical elements but the whole arrangement around PIDs for using and operating them including the ownership, authority, governance and financial elements. The comparison of the different PID schemes resulted in DOI as the preferred option for Digital Specimen (with a tailored metadata schema; Hardisty et al. 2021).

PIDs can uniquely link physical objects to digital artefacts, to records of transactions, the identification of specific vocabulary terms and concepts, etc. Different PID schemes can be used for identifying different things - DOIs for documents and datasets, for example; ORCID for persons, ROR for organisations. These are described in more detail below.

DiSSCo, which is planned to commence full operations in 2026, will have services for indexing, enriching and assisting reuse of specimen data, and needs PIDs and PID services

- to support the ambition for [Digital Specimens](#), virtual collections, workflows, etc. on the Internet;
- for loans and visits like implemented in [ELViS](#), for annotations, citations, attribution of work and microcredits;
- to pursue aims of common policies and procedures; and to transform work practices.

PIDs for Digital Specimens complement identifiers of the physical specimens themselves and/or their corresponding digital database records in institutional collection management systems (Hardisty et al. 2021). Examples of such identifiers include the CETAF Stable Identifiers (Güntsch et al. 2017), the International Geo Sample Numbers (IGSN; Lehnert et al. 2019), GUIDs (Globally Unique Identifier), Darwin Core Triplets (institutionCode:collectionCode:catalogNumber, <https://dwc.tdwg.org/rdf/>), or any other combination of institution/collection codes and catalog numbers.

Community involvement was and is crucial to reach a broad consensus related to the future adoption of certain PID schemes. This has been done via online consultations and discussion forums. A consultation on Digital Specimens Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for the operation of the DiSSCo RI took place in October 2020 (<https://www.dissco.eu/dissco-pid-consultation/>). Another global and virtual consultation hosted by GBIF under the umbrella of the [Alliance for Biodiversity Knowledge](#) has taken place in 2021. In Topic 7 of this community consultation, [Persistent identifier \(PID\) schemes](#) have been discussed.

The discussion on technical convergence of DiSSCo's Digital Specimen concept and the similar concept from the Extended Specimen Network strategy of the Biodiversity Collections Network (BCoN) in the USA (BCoN 2019, Lendemer et al. 2019) is expected to reach consensus on the new term 'Digital Extended Specimen' (DES) circumscribing the Digital Specimen and Extended Specimen ideas in one technical concept.

Terms and acronyms related to and relevant for the DiSSCo infrastructure are described in the **DiSSCo Knowledgebase** [Glossary](#).

2. PIDs relevant for DiSSCo technical infrastructure

2.1 Identifiers for metadata

2.1.1 Identifier for people (researchers and other agents)

Name	Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID iD)
Focus	ORCID provides a persistent digital identifier (an alphanumeric code called ORCID iD), to uniquely identify scientific and other academic authors and contributors.
Further reading	https://orcid.org/ https://github.com/ORCID
Use Cases	Widely used. There are approximately 1235 ORCID member organizations.
Example ID	https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0767-4310 (Alex Hardisty)

Name	Wikidata Q number (QID)
Focus	Wikidata makes use of identifiers for both internal organization of the knowledge base and for its connection to other databases. Wikidata is also a hub/broker for other identifiers.
Further reading	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q43649390 https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Identifiers
Use Cases	Wikidata provides Q numbers for items on people (all those featured in Wikipedia and many more).
Example ID	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q63764 (Louisa Bolus) https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q6694 (Alexander von Humboldt)

Name	International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI)
Focus	ISNI is an ISO certified global standard number especially for contributors to creative works and those active in their distribution, including researchers, inventors, writers, artists, visual creators, performers, producers, publishers, aggregators, and more. The focus is to assign to the public name(s) of those persons a persistent unique identifying number in order to resolve the problem of name ambiguity in search and discovery.

	ISNI aims to act as a bridge identifier across multiple domains and is becoming a component in Linked Data and Semantic Web applications.
Further reading	https://isni.org/
Use Cases	ISNI holds public records of over 12.75 million individuals (of which 2.94 million are researchers) and of 1,588,535 organizations.
Example ID	https://isni.org/isni/0000000032197769 (Amalie Dietrich) https://isni.org/isni/0000000121013124 (Aimé Bonpland)

Name	Virtual International Authority File identifier (VIAF ID)
Focus	VIAF is an international authority file that combines several authority files in an authority data service. It is a joint project of several national libraries and operated by the Online Computer Library Center (OCLC).
Further reading	http://viaf.org/
Use Cases	VIAF identifiers are widely used in library catalogues but also added to biographical articles on Wikipedia and incorporated in Wikidata.
Example ID	https://viaf.org/viaf/98043389/ (Ernst Mayr)

Name	International Plant Name Index (IPNI) ID
Focus	The International Plant Names Index (IPNI) is a nomenclatural index of names of vascular plants from Family down to infraspecific ranks. IPNI IDs are also provided for botanical authors. The older index of authors of plant scientific names is incorporated in IPNI.
Further reading	https://ipni.org/about
Use Cases	International Plant Names Index (IPNI) https://www.ipni.org/ Plants of the World Online (POWO) http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/ World Flora Online (WFO) Portal http://www.worldfloraonline.org/

Example ID	https://www.ipni.org/a/12653-1/ (Carl Linneaus)
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Name	Authors of plant names
Focus	<p>An index of authors of plant scientific names. Includes flowering plants, gymnosperms, pteridophytes, bryophytes, algae, fungi and fossil plants. Full names, dates of birth and death when known, recommended abbreviations and groups in which names have been published, are given for each author.</p> <p>Since 1998, the database of author names and their standard forms has been maintained and updated online as part of The International Plant Names Index (http://www.ipni.org/).</p>
Further reading	<p>http://www.kew.org/data/authors.html https://github.com/tdwg/prior-standards/tree/master/authors-of-plant-names</p> <p>Brummitt & Powell (1992), http://rs.tdwg.org/apn/doc/data/1992</p>
Use Cases	http://www.ipni.org/
Example ID	https://www.ipni.org/a/2432-1

Name	ZooBank authors
Focus	ZooBank, the Official Registry of Zoological Nomenclature, provides UUIDs for currently 83,000+ authors, i.e. anyone who (co-)authored a publication containing nomenclatural acts (e.g. 'original descriptions' of new scientific names for animals, emendations, and lectotypifications) or is contributing to ZooBank content.
Further reading	http://zoobank.org/About
Use Cases	http://zoobank.org/
Example ID	http://zoobank.org/Authors/8C466CBE-3F7D-4DC9-8CBD-26DD3F57E212

2.1.2 Identifier for (research) organizations and their subunits

Name	Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifier
Focus	<p>ROR is a community-led project to develop an open, sustainable, usable, and unique identifier for research organizations of the world. ROR's scope is the affiliation use case and connecting organizations to research outputs.</p> <p>ROR is interoperable with other identifiers and ROR IDs map to GRID, ISNI, Crossref Funder ID, and Wikidata.</p> <p>ROR records include basic metadata about an organization to help with discoverability and disambiguation (including alternate organization names, URL, location, and relationships to other organizations). ROR can support multiple languages and character sets. All ROR IDs and metadata are provided under the Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication.</p>
Further reading	<p>https://ror.org/ https://github.com/ror-community</p>
Use Cases	Focused specifically on the affiliation use case, and widely applied, e.g. in DataCite , Crossref and ORCID datasets.
Example ID	<p>https://ror.org/039zvsn29 (NHM London) https://ror.org/033xtdz52 (Botanic Garden Rio de Janeiro)</p>

Name	Wikidata Q number (QID)
Focus	<p>Wikidata makes use of identifiers for both internal organization of the knowledge base and for its connection to other databases.</p> <p>Wikidata is also a hub/broker for other identifiers.</p>
Further reading	<p>https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q43649390 https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Identifiers</p>
Use Cases	Wikidata also provides QIDs for items on research organizations.
Example ID	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q838691 (MNHN Paris)

Name	Ringgold Identifier (RIN)
Focus	Ringgold Identifiers (Ringgold IDs or RINs) are persistent numeric unique identifiers for organizations in the (scholarly) publishing industry supply chain. Ringgold IDs link to ISNI, IPEDS, NCES, Open Funder Registry IDs. Working to link identifiers with institutional identifiers (e.g. ORCID); ORCID also uses Ringgold IDs.
Further reading	https://www.ringgold.com/ringgold-identifier/
Use Cases	Ringgold's Identify Database contains almost 600,000 organizations in all countries and sectors including academia, corporations, hospitals, and government entities. (only accessible with an account)
Example ID	Ringgold ID 1438 (University of California Berkeley) https://www.ringgold.com/identify-sample/

Name	GBIF Registry of Scientific Collections (GRSciColl)
Focus	GRSciColl is a comprehensive, community-curated clearinghouse of collections information originally developed by Consortium of the Barcode of Life (CBOL). The collections registry includes data about the world's scientific institutions, collections and associated staff members. It spans all scientific disciplines, including earth and space sciences, anthropology, archaeology, biology and biomedicine, as well as applied fields like agriculture, veterinary medicine and technology.
Further reading	https://www.gbif.org/grscicoll https://github.com/gbif/registry Grosjean et al. (2021), https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.5.74354
Use Cases	GBIF is working with partners to establish a standardized, interoperable flow of information between this registry and other key collections infrastructures. GRSciColl runs a weekly synchronization with Index Herbariorum (IH). Following content migration from iDigBio Collections , GRSciColl shares an integrated registry delivering consistent information with shared editing access to users of both GBIF.org and iDigBio.org.
Example ID	https://www.gbif.org/grscicoll/institution/b9684b7b-2550-47a0-93c5-4bb6fc28cea5

2.1.3 Identifier for grant-giving organizations

Name	Crossref Funder Registry (Crossref Funder ID)
Focus	<p>The Crossref Funder Registry is an open and unique registry of persistent identifiers for grant-giving organizations from around the world.</p> <p>The Funder Registry and associated funding metadata allows everyone to have transparency into research funding and its outcomes. It provides grant-giving organization names (funder names), identifiers (funder IDs), and associated grant numbers thus building connections between funders and research outputs.</p> <p>Funding data is used by funders to track the publications resulting from their grants, including use of facilities, equipment, salary awards, etc.</p> <p>The list is available to download as an RDF file, and is freely available under a CCO license waiver.</p>
Further reading	<p>https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/</p> <p>https://www.crossref.org/documentation/content-registration/administrative-metadata/funding-information/</p> <p>https://github.com/CrossRef/open-funder-registry</p>
Use Cases	Used with Open Ukrainian Citation Index (OUCI)
Example ID	https://search.crossref.org/funding?q=501100001659

2.1.4 Identifier for taxa

Name	Catalogue of Life (COL) Stable identifier
Focus	CoL has an algorithm to generate stable identifiers for name usage.
Further reading	<p>https://www.catalogueoflife.org/2021/04/14/stable-ids</p> <p>https://www.catalogueoflife.org/</p> <p>https://data.catalogueoflife.org/</p>
Use Cases	Uses LSIDs as a means of identifying species and higher taxa in these large species catalogue.
Example ID	https://www.catalogueoflife.org/data/taxon/BTB (Lauraceae Juss.)

Name	International Plant Name Index (IPNI) ID
Focus	The International Plant Names Index (IPNI) is a nomenclatural index of names of vascular plants from Family down to infraspecific ranks. IPNI IDs are available for taxon names as well as for author names and publications.
Further reading	https://ipni.org/about
Use Cases	International Plant Names Index (IPNI) https://www.ipni.org/ Plants of the World Online (POWO) http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/ World Flora Online (WFO) Portal http://www.worldfloraonline.org/
Example ID	https://www.ipni.org/n/30117681-2/ (<i>Fragaria</i> × <i>ananassa</i>)

Name	Index Fungorum Registration Identifier
Focus	The Index Fungorum is a global fungal nomenclator that contains names of fungi (including yeasts, lichens, chromistan fungal analogues, protozoan fungal analogues and fossil forms) at all ranks. Index Fungorum uses Registration IDs and UUIDs.
Further reading	http://www.indexfungorum.org/
Use Cases	http://www.indexfungorum.org/
Example ID	http://www.indexfungorum.org/names/NamesRecord.asp?RecordID=550550

Name	World Flora Online (WFO-ID)
Focus	WFO-ID is a unique, immutable identifier for each name in the Backbone, regardless of its taxonomic and nomenclatural status. For machine readability, Representational State Transfer (REST) services are available. WFO-IDs are resolvable as URIs with the prefix "http://www.worldfloraonline.org/taxon/".
Further reading	http://www.worldfloraonline.org/

	Borsch et al. (2020), https://doi.org/10.1002/tax.12373
Use Cases	World Flora Online (WFO) Portal http://www.worldfloraonline.org/
Example ID	http://www.worldfloraonline.org/taxon/wfo-0000173973 (<i>Caesalpinia echinata</i> Lam.)

Name	ZooBank LSID
Focus	ZooBank is a central, authoritative and comprehensive resource for scientific names in zoology. It provides an authoritative online, open-access, community-generated registry for zoological nomenclature (to register new nomenclatural acts, published works, and authors), as a service to taxonomists, biologists, and the global biodiversity informatics community. Life Science Identifiers (LSIDs) are used as globally unique identifiers for ZooBank registration entries.
Further reading	http://zoobank.org/
Use Cases	Official Register of the International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN).
Example ID	http://zoobank.org/NomenclaturalActs/6EA8BB2A-A57B-47C1-953E-042D8CD8E0E2 (<i>Pseudanthias carlsoni</i>)

Name	AlgaeBase PIDs
Focus	AlgaeBase is a database of information on algae that includes terrestrial, marine and freshwater organisms. For convenience, we have included the sea-grasses, even though they are flowering plants.
Further reading	https://www.algaebase.org/about/
Use Cases	https://www.algaebase.org/
Example ID	https://www.algaebase.org/search/species/detail/?species_id=33389

Name	Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) TSN
Focus	ITIS provides authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes of North America and the world. ITIS uses a taxonomic serial number (TSN) system.
Further reading	https://itis.gov/pdf/faq_itis_tsn.pdf
Use Cases	https://itis.gov/
Example ID	https://www.itis.gov/servlet/SingleRpt/SingleRpt?search_topic=TSN&search_value=28759#null

2.1.5 Identifier for localities, geographical names and sites

Name	GeoNames
Focus	GeoNames is an open geographical database that contains over 27 million geographical names and consists of over 12 million unique features. Each GeoNames feature is represented as a web resource identified by a stable URI, links to a HTML Wiki page or provides RDF.
Further reading	https://www.geonames.org/about.html
Use Cases	http://www.geonames.org/
Example ID	https://www.geonames.org/2950159/berlin.html (Berlin)

Name	NGA GeoNames
Focus	National Geospatial intelligence Agency (NGA) GeoNames Search is a database that provides geographic names for the guidance of and use by the Federal Government and for the information of the general public. Geographic names have a Unique Feature Identifier (UFI).

Further reading	https://geonames.nga.mil/gns/html/
Use Cases	https://geonames.nga.mil/namesgaz/
Example ID	

Name	ISO 3166 standard for country codes
Focus	The “ISO 3166 standard – Codes for the representation of names of countries and their subdivisions” was created and is maintained by The International Organization for Standardization (ISO).
Further reading	https://www.iso.org/iso-3166-country-codes.html https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_ISO_3166_country_codes
Use Cases	GBIF https://rs.gbif.org/areas/ IBAN https://www.iban.com/country-codes
Example ID	https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:code:3166:PT

Name	Spatial Reference System Identifier (SRID)
Focus	A SRID is a unique value used to unambiguously identify projected, unprojected, and local spatial coordinate system definitions used by all GIS (geographic information system) applications.
Further reading	https://desktop.arcgis.com/en/arcmap/10.3/manage-data/using-sql-with-gdbs/what-is-an-srid.htm
Use Cases	SRID implementations exist from many different spatial vendors. The EPSG Geodetic Parameter Dataset (or EPSG registry) is one example.
Example ID	

Name	Wikidata Q identifier (Wikidata QID)
Focus	Number with a prefix “q” identifying Wikidata entities.

Further reading	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Identifiers
Use Cases	Wikidata items for geographical names and entities
Example ID	https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q568396 (lake Krumme Lanke in Berlin)

Name	Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names® Online (TGN)
Focus	The TGN is an evolving vocabulary, thousands of TGN place names are added and edited every year. Types of places included in TGN are inhabited places (cities, towns, villages), nations, empires, archaeological sites, named general areas, tribal areas, lost settlements (historically documented, but the precise location is unknown), and physical features. Each record (place concept), name, and much other information in TGN are identified by persistent, unique numeric identifiers.
Further reading	https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/tgn/faq.html
Use Cases	https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/tgn/index.html
Example ID	http://www.getty.edu/vow/TGNFullDisplay?find=Paris&place=&nation=&prev_page=1&english=Y&subjectid=7002980

Name	Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and dataset registry (DEIMS-SDR)
Focus	The aim of DEIMS-SDR is to be the globally most comprehensive catalogue of environmental research and monitoring facilities, featuring foremost but not exclusively information about all LTER sites on the globe and providing that information to science, politics and the public in general.
Further reading	https://deims.org/
Use Cases	https://www.re3data.org/
Example ID	https://deims.org/049de4d9-d7db-4b2c-ace5-de8873f5d277

Name	GADM maps and data
Focus	GADM provides maps of the administrative areas of all countries, at all levels of sub-division. They provide data at high spatial resolutions that include an extensive set of attributes. They have UIDs - may not be considered as PIDs
Further reading	https://gadm.org/formats.html https://gadm.org/about.html
Use Cases	https://gadm.org/
Example ID	

2.2 Identifier for physical objects (collection items, specimens and samples)

Name	Natural Science Identifier (NSId)
Focus	A Natural Science Identifier (NSId) is a universal, unique persistent identifier for digitised natural science specimens (i.e., Digital Specimens) and other associated object types. An NSId will help you unambiguously refer to a specimen you are working with or will help to find a specimen that someone else has told you about by giving you the NSId e.g., as a reference in a journal article. The best DOIs (and other kinds of Handle, including NSId) are opaque ones that carry no information that could potentially become out of date and incorrect.
Further reading	https://disco.tech/2020/05/28/natural-science-identifiers-cetaf-stable-identifiers/ https://pidforum.org/t/a-global-natural-sciences-identifier-nsid-scheme-for-specimens-and-collections/860
Use Cases	
Example ID	

Name	CETAF Stable Identifier (CSI)
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Focus	CETAF stable identifiers provide human- and machine-readable access to specimen information.
Further reading	https://cetaf.org/resources/best-practices/cetaf-stable-identifiers-csi-2/ https://cetafidentifiers.biowikifarm.net/ Güntsch et al. (2017), https://doi.org/10.1093/database/bax003
Use Cases	CETAF Botany Pilot https://services.bgbm.org/botanypilot/ CETAF Stable identifiers have been implemented by various CETAF institutions as well as other partners (see https://know.dissco.eu/handle/item/214).
Example IDs	http://herbarium.bgbm.org/object/B100277113 https://data.rbge.org.uk/herb/E00421509 https://www.botanicalcollections.be/specimen/BR0000005516339

Name	Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
Focus	The DOI system provides a technical and social infrastructure for the registration and use of persistent interoperable identifiers, called DOIs, for use on digital networks. A DOI is a persistent identifier or handle used to identify objects uniquely, standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). DOIs are resolvable and interoperable. DOIs are an implementation of the Handle system.
Further reading	https://www.doi.org/ https://www.doi.org/factsheets/Identifier_Interoper.html
Use Cases	DOIs are widely used mainly to identify academic, professional, and government information, such as journal articles, research reports, data sets, and official publications. However, they have also been used for other types of information resources.
Example ID	

Name	Archival Resource Key (ARK)
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Focus	<p>ARKs are open, mainstream, non-paywalled, decentralized PIDs that identify anything digital, physical, or abstract. The ARK Alliance is an open global community supporting the ARK infrastructure on behalf of research and scholarship.</p> <p>ARKs are being assigned to a variety of different information resources including museum specimens, digitized documents and objects, historic maps, publisher content, genealogical records, scientific records, datasets, journals, etc.</p>
Further reading	<p>https://arks.org/about/</p> <p>https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/ARKs/ARK+Identifiers+FAQ</p>
Use Cases	<p>Since 2001 over 850 organizations across the world have registered and created some 8.2 billion ARKs. The registry includes national and university libraries and archives, art museums, natural history museums, publishers, data centers, government agencies, vendors, and research labs.</p>
Example ID	<p>http://ark.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b8449691v/f29</p>

Name	International Geo Sample Number (IGSN)
Focus	The core purpose of IGSN is to enable transparent and traceable connections between research activities and objects, including samples, collections, instruments, grants, data, publications, people and organizations.
Further reading	<p>https://www.igsn.org/</p> <p>Lehnert et al. (2019), https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.3.37334</p> <p>Buys & Lehnert (2021), https://doi.org/10.5438/thhf-kx17</p>
Use Cases	<p>Operates a central registration system for physical samples.</p> <p>Recent partnership with DataCite that intends to support the global adoption, implementation, and use of physical sample identifiers.</p>
Example ID	<p>http://pid.geoscience.gov.au/sample/AU1243</p>

Name	AAT: Art & Architecture Thesaurus
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Focus	<p>The Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) is a controlled vocabulary used to describe and improve access to information about items of art, architecture, and other material culture. The AAT thesaurus is in compliance with ISO and NISO standards. It is a structured vocabulary of 55,000+ concepts, including terms, descriptions, bibliographic citations, and other information relating to fine art, architecture, decorative arts, archival materials, and material culture.</p> <p>A minimum record in AAT contains a numeric ID, a term, and a position in the hierarchy. AAT could also be used to express that an object in a collection is a “natural” object that occurs in nature and is not made by humans.</p>
Further reading	<p>http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/about.html</p> <p>http://www.getty.edu/vow/AATFullDisplay?find=natural+object&logic=AND&note=&english=N&prev_page=1&subjectid=300404125</p>
Use Cases	<p>http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/</p>
Example ID	<p>http://vocab.getty.edu/page/aat/300404125</p>

2.3 Identifier for literature (scientific articles and other publications)

Name	Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
Focus	<p>The DOI system provides a technical and social infrastructure for the registration and use of persistent interoperable identifiers, called DOIs, for use on digital networks. A DOI is a persistent identifier or handle used to identify objects uniquely, standardized by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO).</p>
Further reading	<p>https://www.doi.org/</p> <p>https://www.doi.org/faq.html</p> <p>https://www.doi.org/factsheets/Identifier Interoper.html</p>
Use Cases	<p>DOIs are widely used mainly to identify academic, professional, and government information, such as journal articles, research reports, data sets, and official publications. However, they have also been used for other types of information resources.</p>
Example ID	<p>https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.7.e67379 (Hardisty et al. 2021)</p>

The [Biodiversity Heritage Library](#) (BHL) is the world’s largest open access digital library for biodiversity literature and archives. BHL has been retrospectively minting DOIs (**#RetroPIDs**) for historic publications since 2011, but the focus has primarily been on monographs. BHL’s new Persistent Identifier Working Group (PIWG) is dedicated to making the content on BHL persistently discoverable, citable and trackable via DOIs and is (at least initially) focusing on journal articles (Kearney 2021).

The International Standard Book Number (**ISBN**) is a numeric commercial book identifier (comprising 13 digits, earlier 10 digits) that is a permanent and citable reference to the related book. Another identifier, the International Standard Serial Number (**ISSN**), identifies periodical publications such as newspapers, magazines and journals. ISBN and ISSN are not PIDs in the strict sense but important identifiers.

2.4 Other identifiers

2.4.1 Identifiers for images or other media

DOIs and repository specific (stable) URIs are used for images, sound, media, etc.

Name	Entertainment Identifier Registry (EIDR)
Focus	EIDR is a global unique identifier system for a broad array of audio visual objects, including motion pictures, television, and radio programs as well as for video service providers, such as broadcast and cable networks. EIDR is an implementation of a digital object identifier (DOI).
Further reading	http://www.eidr.org/
Use Cases	http://www.eidr.org/
Example ID	https://ui.eidr.org/view/content?id=10.5240/EA73-79D7-1B2B-B378-3A73-M (the movie ‘Blade Runner’)

Name	IIIF Manifest
Focus	The International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) is a way to standardize the delivery of images and audio/visual files from servers to different environments on the Web where they can then be viewed and interacted with in many ways. It defines several application programming interfaces designed to operate with the storage and presentation of digitized objects via a web-based interface.

	<p>A IIIF Manifest is the prime unit in IIIF which lists all the information that makes up a IIIF object. It communicates how to display your digital objects, and what information to display about them, including structure, to varying degrees of complexity as determined by the implementer.</p> <p>The Manifest is what is shown in a Viewer and is usually the thing that can be imported into viewers and other tools. It usually represents a physical object such as a book, an artwork, a newspaper issue, etc.</p> <p>The IIIF Manifest is accessible via a URL that points to a document online (in a format called JSON, or JavaScript Object Notation) which a IIIF tool can read and display.</p>
Further reading	https://iiif.io/explainers/using_iiif_resources/ https://iiif.io/explainers/using_iiif_resources/#iiif-manifest
Use Cases	https://projectmirador.org/ https://universalviewer.io/
Example ID	Archive of the poet Dioskoros of Aphrodit

Name	Preston
Focus	<p>Preston is an open-source software system that captures and catalogs biodiversity datasets. It enables reproducible research: scientists can use Preston to work with a uniquely identifiable, versioned copy of all or parts of GBIF-indexed datasets; dataset registry lookups: institutions can use Preston to check if and when their collections have been indexed and made available through iDigBio; cross-network analysis: biodiversity informatics researchers can use Preston to evaluate dataset overlap between GBIF and iDigBio; and finally, decentralized dataset archival: archivists can distribute Preston-generated biodiversity dataset archives across the world.</p>
Further reading	https://github.com/bio-guoda/preston
Use Cases	https://github.com/bio-guoda/preston Preston tracker
Example ID	

2.4.2 Identifier for nucleotide sequence data and genomic data

The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration ([INSDC](#); Arita et al. 2021) is the core infrastructure for sharing nucleotide sequence data (NSD) and the corresponding metadata in the public domain. The collaboration is comprised of three partner organizations that keep the identical information through a daily data exchange process that has operated for over 30 years:

- the DNA Data Bank of Japan ([DDBJ](#)) at the National Institute of Genetics in Mishima, Japan;
- the European Nucleotide Archive ([ENA](#)) at the European Molecular Biology Laboratory's European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) in Hinxton, UK; and
- [GenBank](#) at National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), National Library of Medicine, National Institutes of Health in Bethesda, Maryland, USA.

Name	GenBank (NCBI) accession number
Focus	Sequence IDs are provided by the sequence database GenBank (NCBI).
Further reading	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/sequenceids/
Use Cases	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/
Example ID	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/MG215994.1

Name	BOLD sample IDs
Focus	The Barcode of Life Data System (commonly known as BOLD or BOLDSystems) is a web platform specifically devoted to DNA barcoding. It consists of four main modules, a data portal, an educational portal, a registry of BINs (putative species), and a data collection and analysis workbench.
Further reading	https://v3.boldsystems.org/
Use Cases	
Example ID	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/MG215994.1

2.4.3 Identifier for projects

Name	Research Activity Identifier (RAiD)
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Focus	<p>RAiD is a unique and persistent identifier for research projects. A research project is an activity that takes place over a period of time, has a set scope, is resourced by researchers, research support staff and uses and produces data.</p> <p>RAiD acts as a container for research project activities by collecting identifiers for the people, publications, instruments and institutions that are involved.</p>
Further reading	<p>https://www.raid.org.au/ https://ardc.edu.au/services/identifier/</p> <p>ISO standard under development: https://www.iso.org/standard/75931.html</p>
Use Cases	
Example ID	

2.4.4 Identifier for instruments

Instruments are employed in numerous and diverse scientific disciplines and essential for the creation of research data. An instrument, i.e. a *measuring instrument*, is defined as a “device used for making measurements, alone or in conjunction with one or more supplementary devices” (VIM 2021). Given the importance of instruments and their associated metadata to the assessment of data quality and data reuse, globally unique, persistent and resolvable identification of instruments is crucial. PID assignment for instruments will facilitate the easy implementation of instruments in the metadata for both scientific data publications and journal article publications.

Information about instrumentation used in research has often been missing, but domain specific initiatives have progressed significantly on the implementation of instrument metadata. PID assignment for instruments is now possible and is expected to gain wider adoption in the natural science community in the future.

Name	Persistent Identifier for instruments (DOI, Handle)
Focus	<p>The Research Data Alliance Working Group Persistent Identification of Instruments (PIDINST) developed a community-driven solution for persistent identification of instruments.</p> <p>PIDINST developed a universal metadata schema and prototyped schema implementation with DataCite and ePIC as representative persistent identifier infrastructures and with HZB (Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie) and BODC (British Oceanographic Data Centre) as representative institutional instrument providers.</p>

Further reading	Stocker et al. (2020), http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-018 Buys et al. (2020), https://doi.org/10.5438/tdk2-2g94 https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/persistent-identification-instruments-wg
Use Cases	Rolling Deck to Repository (R2R), SENSOR Information System infrastructure
Example ID	

Name	International Geo Sample Number (IGSN)
Focus	An International Geo Sample Number (IGSN) provides an unambiguous globally unique persistent identifier for physical samples. IGSN aims to enable transparent and traceable connections between research activities and objects, including samples, collections, instruments, grants, data, publications, people and organizations.
Further reading	https://www.igsn.org/ Lehnert et al. (2019), https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.3.37334
Use Cases	Operates a central registration system for physical samples. Recent partnership with DataCite that intends to support the global adoption, implementation, and use of physical sample identifiers.
Example ID	

2.4.5 Identifiers for collecting events / collection objects

Such identifiers do not exist at present. There could be an identifier for a collecting event such as a moth trap etc. or a collection object which would include all the preparations within it and generally defined by the collector + collector number.

2.4.6 Identifier for trait data

Name	Identifier for trait datasets (DOI)
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Focus	The Plant trait database TRY is using DOIs for datasets comprising trait data.
Further reading	https://www.try-db.org/TryWeb/Submission.php
Use Cases	TRY is working in close collaboration with the Latin American initiative DiverSus (CONICET-Universidad Nacional de Córdoba) and the British Royal Botanical Garden Kew
Example ID	

2.4.7 Identifier for antibodies, model organisms, cell lines and plasmids

Name	Antibodies Registry ID
Focus	The Antibody Registry gives researchers a way to universally identify antibodies used in their research. The Antibody Registry assigns unique and persistent identifiers to each antibody so that they can be referenced within publications.
Further reading	https://antibodyregistry.org/about https://scicrunch.org/resources
Use Cases	
Example ID	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:AB_2178887

Name	Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs)
Focus	The Resource Identification Portal (RRID Portal) was created in support of the Resource Identification Initiative , which aims to promote research resource identification, discovery, and reuse. The portal offers a central location for obtaining and exploring Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs) - persistent and unique identifiers for referencing a research resource such as Antibodies, Model Organisms, Cell Lines, Plasmids, and other Tools (software, databases, services).
Further reading	https://scicrunch.org/resources

Use Cases	https://scicrunch.org/resources
Example ID	https://scicrunch.org/resolver/RRID:AB_2178887

2.4.8 Identifier for software

Name	Software Heritage
Focus	It provides unique identifiers, intrinsically bound to the software components. This will ensure that a resilient web of knowledge can be built on top of the Software Heritage archive.
Further reading	https://www.softwareheritage.org/mission/
Use Cases	https://www.softwareheritage.org/
Example ID	SoftWare Heritage persistent IDentifiers (SWHIDs) Example: swh:1:cnt:94a9ed024d3859793618152ea559a168bbcbb5e2

2.4.9 Identifier for patents

Name	The Lens - Free & Open Patent and Scholarly Search
Focus	Lens is an online patent and scholarly literature search facility that provides global patent and scholarly knowledge as a public good to inform science and technology. It collaborates with the open access scholarly and open data initiatives, the services are embedded in global public resources like PubMed.
Further reading	https://www.lens.org/
Use Cases	https://www.lens.org/
Example ID	https://www.lens.org/lens/patent/004-676-988-641-380/fulltext?l=en

2.5 Overview of PIDs used for different use cases

	DOI	Wikidata QID	URI	ORCID	ROR	UUID (GUID)	LSID	ARK
People		x		x		(x)	(x)	
Organizations		(x)	(x)		x			
Taxa		(x)	x			x	x	
Localities / sites		x	(x)					
Physical Specimens	(x)		x					x
Digital Specimens	x		(x)			(x)		x
Literature	x		x					x
Images or other media	x							x
Instruments	(x)							
Transaction events						x		

3. Discussion

Community involvement has long been important for the development of PIDs in biocollections (Guralnick et al. 2015) and ongoing discussions in the NSC community related to PIDs are happening during consultations (see above) and on platforms such as the PID Forum. The [PID Forum](#) is a global information and discussion platform for persistent identifiers (PIDs), which was initiated by the [FREYA project](#) and is now hosted by [NISO](#), the National Information Standards Organization. The PIDforum brings together different research communities working with PIDs and provides a virtual place for sharing best practices (Knowledge Hub), announcing events, asking questions, and having discussions about PIDs (Braukmann et al. 2020).

DiSSCo will not be directly using all of the above-mentioned PIDs or other identifiers. However, it is important to be aware of other developments due to interoperability reasons and to participate in initiatives that support interoperability.

The matrix presented above (Section 2.5) gives an overview of PID systems used for different use cases. While some PID systems are applied for various use cases (e.g. DOIs or Wikidata QIDs), others PIDs are very specific and have been developed for single use cases. In addition, the matrix shows which use cases are using several identifier systems which could limit interoperability.

During the global consultation, the different concepts of sample, specimen, material sample, and subsample had to be clarified. While a material sample is the result of a sampling event, a (catalogued) specimen is the result of a curation process applied to a material sample. Nevertheless, there are some categories of curated objects, i.e. specimens that are not material samples, such as sound recordings or drawings. Specimens can yield subsamples that can themselves be curated (and thus become specimens with identifiers).

Standardizing metadata for heterogeneous sample collections is a present challenge. Beyond samples/specimens, people and organizations are involved with collections, in the curation and management of samples. These persons (agents) need PIDs, such as ORCID IDs and Wikidata QIDs, and ROR IDs for organizations.

Some identifiers gained general importance during the last years. ROR is not only included in DataCite, Crossref and ORCID datasets, it has also been adopted more widely in the NSC community. ROR has reached a level of community adoption that will ensure its long-term place in the persistent identifier and data infrastructure environment. ROR is interoperable with other identifiers and ROR IDs map to GRID (Global Research Identifier Database), ISNI, Crossref Funder ID, and Wikidata.

Since ROR's focus is on the "affiliation use case" identifying organizations and related research outputs, it will probably become more widely used in describing affiliations (formal relationships) and linking between researchers and organizations associated with those researchers, including but not limited to their employer, educator, funder, or scholarly society.

There are numerous different people identifiers, some are more widely used than others, and partly also link to other identifiers. ORCID IDs are becoming widely used in the scientific community. However, there are users that do not want to get an ORCID ID due to e.g. its compulsory use by some publishers, GDPR issues, etc. For deceased persons, the Wikidata QIDs might become a means of choice since it serves also as a hub for many other identifiers. For DiSSCo, current plans involve the use

of ORCID IDs and Wikidata QIDs for people but referring to other identifiers in the metadata should also be possible.

DOIs are the most widely adopted persistent identifier in research data repository systems (Klump & Huber 2017). While the underlying DOI system has a strong commercial backing, other PID systems such as URN and ARK have the backing of national libraries. Sustainability is an essential aspect of PID systems and as Klump & Huber (2017) point out “they do not come for free”. To ensure the persistence, resolvability, and discoverability for long periods (e.g., 100+ years) entails a cost. This cost, however, is not so high if compared to the value of research and economic opportunities lost because objects are not properly identified, research datasets lost, etc.

Handle System mechanisms are proposed as the underlying technical and operational infrastructure making the PIDs needed by the natural sciences community persistent and resolvable. DiSSCo will adopt a ‘driven-by DOI’ persistent identifier (PID) scheme customised to the needs of the natural sciences community (Hardisty et al. 2021). This proposal of adopting DOI as the PID for Digital Specimens is based on a substantial evaluative comparison of 22 Handle System variants (Hardisty et al. 2021).

The cost of operating an appropriate PID scheme based on the Handle System is estimated to be around €1m/\$1.2m annually for the 30 billion PIDs needed for Digital extended Specimens in natural history domains. The cost could be shared globally among institutions and/or various research infrastructures but there should be no costs for individual researchers to make use of PIDs.

Other initiatives are also facing the decision to choose the best PID system (e.g. [Heritage PIDs](#)) or are working on a sustainable business model to scale to growing demands (IGSN, Global Sample Number, a popular PID currently mostly applied to physical earth samples). The experience of these initiatives can be helpful throughout the process of implementing PIDs in DiSSCo.

DiSSCo has become a [member](#) of the International DOI Foundation (IDF) and is working to develop the governance, operations, financing, and service portfolio models, potentially for a new Registration Agency (RA) operating on behalf of the global community. Establishing such a new RA is a practical way forward to support the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable; Wilkinson et al. 2016) data architecture of DiSSCo research infrastructure. This approach is compatible with the policies of the [European Open Science Cloud](#) (EOSC) and is aligned to existing practices across the global community of natural science collections.

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